

PROCEEDINGS OF THE

31st International Symposium
on Analytical and Environmental Problems

Szeged, Hungary
October 13-14, 2025

University of Szeged

Edited by:
Tünde Alapi
Róbert Berkecz
István Ilisz

Publisher:
University of Szeged, H-6720 Szeged, Dugonics tér 13,
Hungary

ISBN 978-963-688-078-1

2025.
Szeged, Hungary

***The 31st International Symposium on Analytical and
Environmental Problems***

Organized by:

SZAB Kémiai Szakbizottság Analitikai és Környezetvédelmi Munkabizottsága

Supporting Organizations

Hungarian Academy of Sciences

Hungarian Chemical Society Group of Csongrád County

Institute of Pharmaceutical Analysis, University of Szeged

Department of Molecular and Analytical Chemistry, University of Szeged

Symposium Chairman:

István Ilisz, DSc

Honorary Chairman:

Zoltán Galbács, PhD

Organizing Committee:

István Ilisz, DSc

professor of chemistry

University of Szeged, Institute of Pharmaceutical Analysis

Tünde Alapi, PhD

associate professor

University of Szeged, Department of Molecular and Analytical Chemistry

Róbert Berkecz, PhD

associate professor

University of Szeged, Institute of Pharmaceutical Analysis

Scientific Committee:

István Ilisz, DSc

Tünde Alapi, PhD

Róbert Berkecz, PhD

Daniela Sojic Merkulov, PhD

full professor

*University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and
Environmental Protection*

ENHANCED SOLUBILIZATION OF KETOPROFEN USING TRITON X-100, TRITON X-165, BRIJ C10, AND THEIR MIXED MICELLE SYSTEMS

Zita Farkaš Agatić¹, Mladena Lalić-Popović¹, Nemanja Todorović¹, Ana Stjepanović¹, Vesna Tepavčević¹, Mirjana Bećarević¹, Mihalj Poša¹

¹Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

e-mail: zita.farkas@mf.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Ketoprofen, a Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) class II drug, exhibits poor aqueous solubility, which limits its bioavailability and therapeutic performance. To address this, we investigated micellar systems composed of Triton X-100, Triton X-165, and Brij C10, studied individually and in binary and ternary mixtures, with the aim of enhancing solubilization efficiency. Critical micelle concentrations (*cmc*) were determined by fluorescence spectroscopy using pyrene as a probe, and the thermodynamics of mixed micelle formation were evaluated by Rubingh's model, Regular Solution Theory, and the Margules function to obtain interaction parameters and excess Gibbs free energies. Solubilization of ketoprofen was quantified by HPLC in terms of molar solubilization ratios and partition coefficients. Brij C10 exhibited the lowest *cmc* and the highest solubilization capacity, with molar solubilization ratios exceeding 6, while Triton micelles showed lower efficiency. Binary Brij–Triton mixtures revealed synergistic stabilization but occasional antagonistic solubilization, highlighting a trade-off between stability and drug incorporation. The ternary system, although thermodynamically stable, showed reduced solubilization due to compact packing. Overall, Brij-rich systems proved to be the most effective carriers, combining low *cmc* with high solubilization efficiency. These findings provide a thermodynamic basis for the rational design of surfactant mixtures for the solubilization of poorly water-soluble drugs.

Introduction

Ketoprofen, a widely used NSAID, suffers from low aqueous solubility despite high permeability, placing it in BCS Class II. Improving its solubility is critical for enhancing oral bioavailability. Micellar solubilization is a versatile approach, as surfactants self-assemble above the *cmc* to incorporate hydrophobic drugs. Mixed micelles can outperform single surfactants due to synergistic interactions. TX100 and TX165 are polyoxyethylene-based non-ionic surfactants of varying hydrophilicity, while BC10 is a Brij surfactant with strong hydrophobic contribution. The study aims to clarify how these systems, alone and in mixtures, influence micelle stability and ketoprofen uptake.

Experimental

- ***cmc* determination:** Fluorescence spectroscopy with pyrene probe at 278.15–318.15 K.
- **Thermodynamic analysis:** Rubingh's model, Regular Solution Theory, and Margules equations used to calculate β , ΔG^E , ΔS^E , and ΔH^E .
- **Solubilization studies:** Ketoprofen quantification via HPLC on C18 column, isocratic mobile phase (acetonitrile:acetic acid 65:35 v/v), detection at 330 nm. MSR, Δ MSR, and K_m calculated to assess solubilization efficiency.

Results and Discussion

- **cmc values:** BC10 showed the lowest *cmc* (0.018–0.020 mmol·dm⁻³), consistent with its hydrophobic chain. TX100 and TX165 *cmc* values matched literature (0.2–0.6 mmol·dm⁻³).
- **Binary mixtures:** BC10 + TX165 exhibited the strongest synergism ($\beta \approx -4.8$; $g^E \approx -2300 \text{ J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ at 318 K). TX100 + BC10 showed composition-dependent behaviour, with negative g^E near equimolar ratios but positive values in BC10-rich mixtures.
- **Ternary mixture:** Though g^E was negative at most temperatures, indicating stability, compact micellar packing reduced drug accommodation.
- **Solubilization:** BC10 micelles achieved the highest molar solubilization ratio (MSR) (>6). Triton-only systems had MSR <1. Binary Brij-Triton micelles improved stability but sometimes showed antagonistic ΔMSR . K_m values followed hydrophobicity: BC10 > TX165/BC10 > TX100/BC10.
- **Temperature effects:** At lower T, micellization was enthalpy-driven ($h^E < 0$), while at higher T entropy became dominant ($s^E > 0$), reflecting hydration changes and chain flexibility.

Figure 1. The TX165/BC10 mixed micelle

Figure 2. MSR values for single, binary, and ternary systems.

Conclusion

Micellar stability and drug solubilization efficiency are not directly correlated. Brij C10 micelles provide the strongest ketoprofen solubilization, while ternary mixtures highlight that excessive stabilization can reduce drug loading. These findings emphasize the need to balance stability and flexibility in surfactant design. Rational formulation using Brij-containing systems offers a promising strategy for BCS Class II drugs.

References

- [1] D.N. Rubingh, in: K.L. Mittal, (Ed.), Solution Chemistry of Surfactants, Springer, New York, NY, USA, 1979, pp. 337.
- [2] M. Poša, J. Chem. Thermodyn. 140 (2020) 105914.
- [3] M.E.N.P. Ribeiro, C.L. de Moura, M.G.S. Vieira, N.V. Gramosa, C. Chaibundit, M.C. de Mattos, D. Attwood, S.G. Yeates, S.K.Nixon, N.M.P.S. Ricardo. Int. J. Pharm. 436 (2012) 631.